

ISic3392

I.Sicily inscription 3392

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solanto

Provenance

plaque in a wall of a house on via Castello 7, Solanto

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Solanto, private house

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR137139

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Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491427

EDR 137139

EDCS 46600169

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

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1923-. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. Supplementum epigraphicum
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